
CAPACITY BUILDING FOR ENGINEERS AND GEOSCIENTISTS: AS ESSENTIAL TOOL TOWARDS THE REALIZATION OF NIGERIA'S VISION 20:2020

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade Nigerian has made attempt to liberalize its investment regime for mining by establishing the Mining Cadastre and privatizing formerly state-owned mineral assets. In response, Nigeria has in recent times witnessed increased interest in foreign direct mineral investment. The restructuring of fiscal and regulatory regime to encourage foreign investment, and the associated anticipated influx of mining capital, technology and skills will require appropriate capacity building in the mineral sector in order to transform traditional relationships between mining firms, local communities and the government. This transformation necessitates a re-evaluation of the technical capacity to capture the expected increased economic and social benefits from mineral production. Consequently, the challenges associated with capacity building in mining institutions are highlighted with the view of reviewing the roles of the private sector and government within the context of global economy. The paper considers effective mechanism for improving Nigeria's capacity building in the mineral sector in order to maximize the economic and social benefits of mineral production for the purpose of achieving the vision 20:2020

INTRODUCTION

Vision 2020 is a comprehensive framework designed to stimulate economic growth in the country. The framework also offers a blueprint for sustainable political development in Nigeria. Vision 2020 is aligned with the goals of the National Development Plan (NDP). One of the main objectives of Vision 2020 is to place Nigeria in the top 20 leading economies of the world by the year 2020. To achieve this objective, Nigeria would have to compete with nations like the United States, Japan, Germany, China, and the United Kingdom, which have traditionally maintained the Top Five ranking of the International Monetary Fund (IMF). In 2007, IMF ranked Brazil 10, India 12, South Korea 13, and Indonesia 20 respectively. These nations are expected to vigorously compete with Nigeria in the global economy. Nigeria is ranked 41. The IMF uses criteria based on several benchmarks such as the Gross Domestic Products (GDP), the Gross National Product (GNP), the rise in personal income etc (International Monetary Fund, 2007). The question worth answering is which of these afore-mentioned top ranking developing countries does Nigeria expects to surpass by the year 2020?

Effective training of Mining Engineers and Geoscientists is a tool for change that ensures the advancement of all Nations of the world. The much needed knowledge can only be imparted through effective capacity building of the personnel. This entails value addition to knowledge through effective development of the human mind to face new scientific challenges in mineral exploration, development and exploitation of mineral resources for economic development and transformation. In order to succeed in the current world of globalization or knowledge economy, the Nigerian mineral sector would require adequate talented and knowledgeable workforce (Abdulkarim, 2009). In the present competitive world, even developed nations need to have abundance of talented and highly intelligent and knowledgeable workers to be able to compete or remain competitive in the international market places. Capacity building would require good education system with an advance private industrial mining sector base to provide the much needed platform for hands-on-the- job training.

Our Mining Engineering degree programme of the 21st century should provide the knowledge and understanding of geology, rock mechanics, engineering design, economics, surveying, and management and associated practical skills that will enable graduates to make valuable contribution as soon as they are employed. In larger companies, work often involves the management of multidisciplinary teams of engineers and scientists(Aina, 1998) . Because of this, mining engineering degrees should be very wide ranging to provide an excellent basis for careers in technical management.

The President's Seven-Point Agenda (polity, micro-economy, infrastructure, education, health, agriculture, and manufacturing) supports the goals of the actualization of Vision 20:2020. By implication therefore, federal government's expectations are: Education – a modern and vibrant education system which provides for every Nigerian the opportunity and facility to achieve his maximum potential and provides the country with adequate and competent manpower; and Manufacturing– a vibrant and globally competitive manufacturing sector that must contribute significantly to GDP with a manufacturing value added of less than 40%. (Abdullahi, 2009)

In order to achieve the vision 20:2020, Nigeria must evolve an education system that can be more functional and geared more towards educating people in areas that will help build the economy and improve the society generally (Abdullahi S.A. 2009). To this effect, and in order that the above sectors can advance, capacity building of personnel must take precedence to ensure the exploitation of the much needed industrial raw materials that contribute to the development and advancement of all sectors of the national economy. Consequently, there is the need for Nigeria to focus in graduating mining and related engineers, scientists and technologies particularly for the mineral sector which provides the base line for industrial advancement.

AN OVERVIEW OF MINING EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

In pre-independent Nigeria, the training of mining or technical personnel was largely a private venture by mining companies. The pioneer mining school in Jos was responsible for production of holders of Ordinary National Diplomas (OND), also was the Coal Corporation Training School, Enugu. The graduates adequately filled the middle class technical manpower requirements of the mining industries then, while further training was accomplished in Europe, Canada, the United States and United Kingdom (Mallo,1999).

A survey of relevant tertiary institutions in Nigeria shows that out of the over 95 Polytechnics and 120 universities, (Private, state and Federal inclusive), only six Polytechnics and one University (The Plateau State Polytechnic, Auchu Polytechnic, Idah Polytechnic, Kogi State Polytechnic, Ado Ekiti Polytechnic and Federal University of Technology, Akure) offer National/Higher National Diplomas in Mining Engineering, Mineral Processing and Bachelor of Technology in Mining Engineering respectively. Most of the Mining Departments are poorly equipped with the necessary laboratory, library and information technology. In spite of the inadequacies, hundreds of graduates are produced and released into the unemployment market with both no sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge of the disciplines. Statistically it can be confirmed that from 1975 to 2005 the total number of graduate produced in these institutions may conservatively put only at about 1000. This number is grossly inadequate for a functional mineral industry with a mineral resources capacity such as Nigeria.

That presently, no Nigerian University is listed amongst the first 30 Universities in Africa, and in the 1000 of lists of world universities, points to the fact that even the University of Technology Akure – the only University that offers Mining Engineering at Degree level may falls short of the required capacity to produce the much needed high skilled graduates that can meet international standards.

In 2008 the NBTE unveiled plans to introduce Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech) programmes in Polytechnics across the country. The motive, which is to enhance Technical Education, indicates that the programmes is to be run by Polytechnics with adequate resources and experience in running Higher National Diploma. The Federal Government also approved the establishment of Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VETs) and Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IETs). These institutions are expected to accommodate the multitude of secondary school leavers and encourage private sector participation in skills acquisition and training. The aim is to widen access to technical and vocational education and serve the needs of emerging industries and for self development (Yakubu 2008). The establishment of the Nigerian Institute of Mining and Geosciences is intended to strengthen the capacity building of personnel in the mineral industry in line with the new reforms. Scientific and Technological infrastructures in Mining take decades to develop. The training of a scientific cadre is itself a long-term effort.

The student work experience in Mining Engineering and relevant disciplines is managed through the collaboration of the Federal Government, the industrial Training Fund (ITF), the accrediting agencies – national Universities Commission (NUC) the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) as well as the Employers of Labour and Institutions offering Mining/Mineral Resources Engineering. Each of the aforementioned bodies has specific roles to play in the management of the SIWES. The provisions of Federal Decree No. 47 of 197 (as amended in 1990) makes it mandatory on all ministries, companies and parastatals to offer places for the attachment of students to industries(Olawumi, 1998). In recent times efforts have made to strengthen the

capacities of these various bodies to deliver on their responsibilities. However, much is still to be achieved in view of competing demands on the Federal government. With the requisite practical training while the Degree students would blend their theoretical knowledge with a well-supervised SIWES by the Industrial Training Fund (Olu, 2000). The present structure of Polytechnic education is that a student should first come for two years ND Programme and proceed for one year of industrial training in relevant profession. The idea of acquiring one year of Industrial Experience is commendable however, this arrangement is defective. For instance, neither the NBTE, Industrial placement unit nor the Polytechnics have control as to where the students undergo the 12 months post ND mandatory industrial hands-on- training(Mallo,2000). The paucity of relevant functional mining concerns in the country further aggravates the situation. The aim of the programme is to bridge the identified gap between theory and practice of engineering and technology. The industrial attachment is also expected to prepare participating Students for the world of work through their exposure to augment theoretical works. In the process students get exposed to various equipment and machines especially with regards to operations and maintenance. Experience has shown that of about 35 students who usually return for HND programmes not less than 5% undergo the compulsory one year industrial training. In recent years mining companies have continued to produce at below their capacity. This makes it exceedingly difficult for them to recruit new employees. The question is how an organization that is reducing staff due to economic down turn can be forced to take the financial burden of one year industrial training of ND graduates. The full benefit of mining/technical education as conceived and outlined in the national policy on education and in the national policy on science and technology can be achieved only if the nation's strategy rests on four essential pillars:

- a) The creation of awareness that mining is the bed-rock of industrialization
- b) The creation of awareness to the inculcation and development of a science culture in the citizenry
- c) Exploitation of science and Technology to transform over abundant mineral resources into goods and services and
- 4) Utilization of acquired wealth to facilitate improvement in the quality of life.

It must be recognized, further that science and technology also depends on other institutions: Financial institutions to finance R & D and other S & T investments; Training institutions which train scientists and associated personnel and Markets through which knowledge intensive goods breakdown of relative R & D intent and services are traded. There is also, Institution for sharing and dissemination of scientific and technological knowledge, such as professional associations.

In mining engineering, these skills can be combined in variable proportion. For example mine technological occupation such as production drilling involves both routinized and conceptual skills. Mining institutions have experimented with various methods of transmitting abstract and problem – solving skills and applied skills. Of these the most potent method of training remains on-the-job- training. From the aforementioned constraints it can be clearly seen why the Mining Engineering students find it difficult if not impossible to acquire the necessary industrial exposure in government related companies.

Mining engineering education has remained in its rudimentary stage for the following reasons:-

1. The discovery of oil and over-dependence of the country on this commodity, political, fiscal/ policy and economic decline/instability.
2. The misconceptions on the nature and purpose of mining engineering education have hindered its development and growth.
3. The existing curricula are not being revised fast enough to keep pace with current rapid technological changes; they therefore, lack the dynamism and responsiveness needed to meet the new demands of the society and the mineral industry. The best practice is a thoughtful and thorough design of the curriculum with significant input from the industry as well as peer review mechanism by the academia.
4. The decline of mineral production and employment opportunities in the formal industrial and manufacturing sectors has led to the decline in knowledge and interest in mining engineering
5. Perhaps because of a combination of the above problems, there is a low and unbalanced patronage of mining engineering education across the country and across trades.
6. Inadequate funding and qualified staffing continue to reflect on the performance of the products of some mining engineering departments.

EXPERIENCES FROM BEST-PRACTICES

The international best practice is the training of Engineers and Geo-scientists that can be deployed to work with multinational mining companies all over the world. Consequently, mining Engineering offers a truly rewarding and exciting career, taking one practically all over the world, and working with wide range of engineering professionals and environmental engineers. This exciting field of endeavour does not just deal with safe and profitable extraction of valuable minerals from the ground, but also involves the exotic construction of highly specialized projects, such as the tunnels channels, dip metal mines, massive mine layouts etc. The scale of mining and processing operations can be immense and they require teams of trained professional engineers. Mining and Quarry engineers design and operate the systems used in the extraction of ores. The profession offers intimate hands- on experiences with various aspects of drilling, blasting (explosives), heavy earth moving equipment, as well as utilize state of the art computer aided design and management of operations.

The training of the mining engineer offer a wide-range career prospects owing to the diversity and geographical spread of the industry. The graduates of mining/mineral processing engineering find employment in quarrying and tunneling, oilfield development, heavy and specialist chemical manufacture, extractive metallurgy and planning, environmental control, equipment design, and manufacture, consultancy and research etc. Mining safety engineers use their knowledge of mine design and practices to ensure the safety of workers and to comply with State and Federal safety regulations. They inspect the surfaces of walls and roofs, monitor air quality, and examine mining equipment for compliance with safety practices (Paul, 1991). Mining engineers are generally well remunerated and most mining companies offer attractive fringe benefits. The best practice ensures that skill acquisition in mining engineering takes into consideration: cognizanc:

1. Manual dexterity or practiced ability also known as routinized skills.
2. Application of expertise or a body of theoretical knowledge also known as applied skills.
3. Ability to solve abstract conceptual problems also known as conceptual skills.

The Asian Tigers and other African countries have in the last 50 years made insignificant efforts in the development of capacity of its citizenry in science and Technology. The Asian Tigers made early efforts at building capacity by focusing on building and equipping educational faculties in addition to massive training of experts abroad to staff them. Emphasis was on colleges and universities, agricultural research stations and extension programmes, and other R&D facilities (Mohammed 2000). More recently, efforts have included support for standards, intellectual rights and other institutions. Apprenticeship and traineeship approach to capacity building has received appropriate patronage in some countries notably Australia, Canada, etc. An apprenticeship involves full-time work with an employer who provides an opportunity to learn all aspects of a trade. This is a structured program for a fixed period of time (usually four years) and while you learn on the job, you also attend off the job training at a TAFEWA college or another registered training provider. On the other hand, in a traineeship the students also gain hands-on skills and work experience, and improve their employment prospects, while earning a wage. On successful completion the candidate will gain a nationally recognized qualification which can lead to rewarding options for careers progression. The difference between a traineeship and an apprenticeship is that a traineeship can be either a full-time or part-time employment-based training arrangement, usually for 12 months or more, generally in a non-trade related area (Costa, 2009). As at 2007 the minerals and energy sector has remained the second-highest employer of trainees and apprenticeships and is the fifth largest employer overall in WA. 90% of CME members employ apprentices. 65% of CME members employ trainees. Some of the benefits of an apprenticeship are as follows:

1. Earning a wage while on training for careers in mining or oil and gas jobs
2. Learning on-the-job skills combined with off-the-job training
3. Acquisition of a nationally recognized qualification on successful completion and
4. Taking a valuable step towards a rewarding career in resources or progression.

In America, Mineral Resources Engineering institutions utilize the industrial experiences of industrialist, and engineers working in the Mineral Industries. The objective is to recognize the achievements of individuals who had have exceptional career in mining and related industries and invite them to present their unique experiences to the Mining Engineering Faculty/Departments of Mining engineering Institutions. The nominees who emerge through a constituted selected committee can either be alumnus or non-alumnus who has exceptional achievements and unique experiences in the mining and related industries. Each year two candidates are selected one at the First semester and the other at the second semester. The sourcing of resource persons from other countries are considered as viable alternatives.

A committee of employers of labour is established to periodically interact with undergraduates in Mining institutions the visiting committee comprises of representatives of organizations that usually employ Bachelor, Master of Sciences and Doctorate students of American mining institutions. The committee fulfils an important role in the department by providing feedback which ensures that students graduating at all levels have the skills that they require to be marketable. During their periodic-annual meeting, the committee members have separate interactive sessions with Vice-Chancellors, Faculty members, the undergraduates' students, graduate students and other relevant College Administrators. The findings of the committee is finally incorporated in the service delivery to enhance the learning of mining/ mineral processing engineering and Engineering geology are tailored towards specific needs of the employers of labour.

The computer/communication (IT) revolution is going on world-wide. The trend has succeeded in making the world a "global village" this is because there is hardly any sphere of human endeavour that is not affected by the information technology. The mineral industry has gone through transformation from the world of simulation modeling of mining systems, mine evaluation to animation of technological processes associated with the mineral industry. The best practice in modern capacity building requires the provision of a Mining, MinE Teaching and Design Computer laboratory. This laboratory should be equipped with PC computers, a digitizer, a LaserJet printer, an inkjet printer, and a large formatted plotter.

The mine design laboratory should also be provided with specialized software tools for undergraduate and post graduate mining engineering classes as follows:

Engineering CAD class provides AutoCAD drawing skills for the lower classes of mining/mineral processing engineering students for construction of process flow sheet and mine surveying maps. Cogo-Design and DTM – contour of SurvCADD is also used in the class to provide the skills of importing the surveying data points, drawing surface contours of stratum volume between final ground (surface) and original ground (surface), using the grid and two surface volume methods.

Similarly, exploration mapping, reserve valuation, surface mining and underground mining systems classes provide the skills of designing the geological columns, reserve estimation, economic analysis, surface mining and underground mining systems to the students using a combination of spreadsheet, AutoCAD, and Advanced Mining system of SurvCAD.

On the other hand, the coal preparation class provides the skills of designing the process flow sheet including mass balance calculations, quality and quantity of clean coal product prediction based on the size distribution, washability analysis, and efficiency of the separators, to the students. The combination of spreadsheets, AutoCAD and PSIPLOT are used for these purposes.

THE CHALLENGES

Fiscal challenges to capacity building in Higher Education Institutions offering Mining and related Engineering disciplines include:

1. The absence of career Counseling and crazy for paper qualifications is the major reason that 85% of intakes into mining and related disciplines have no engineering appeal.
2. Financing of education has drastically plummeted to an all time low making the acquisition of state of the art technology impossible.
3. The tendency of unit costs in higher education to rise faster than the unit costs in the overall economy. This tendency is accelerated by the very rapidly increasing costs of technology and by the rapid change in the fields of study in great need and /demand
4. The increasing scarcity of public revenue leading to budgetary constraints by government. The situation is further worsened by the competing demands on health care, security, environmental stabilization and restoration, poverty alleviation, sustenance of democratic institutions etc. The inability of government to rely on former methods of raising public revenues, such as turnover on state-owned enterprises and dwindling revenues from commodity trades has aggravated the financial capacity to provide adequate funding.
5. Political considerations in line with international best practices of drift towards the market solutions, including privatization, deregulation, and decentralization of public enterprise. There is growing dissatisfaction with the slow-pace of reforms in the mineral industry which inhibits the growth of the public sector towards modern market solutions.

6. Government regulation and control poses a challenge to Nigerian Higher institutions as it affects the autonomy of the systems, and the role of external agencies in ensuring the stability of the systems. The Nigerian Universities Commission and the National Board for Technical Education are directly the regulatory bodies over institutions that offer Mining Engineering disciplines. The funding of the Federal Institutions through these regulatory systems has been inadequate thereby reversing the process of devolution that gave the states and private sector increasing responsibility for higher as well as primary and secondary education. The situation is more compounding with NBTE necessitating the call by stakeholders for creation of a separate Board to be known as National Board of the Monotechnics and Technical Schools from the present NBTE.

THE WAY FORWARD

The education system must incorporate the needed skills development and given the urgent priority it requires for industrial development. This trend was adopted by the Asian Tigers who today form part of the 20 developed economies of the world. Nigeria, may take the right step of effective utilization of its oil resources for the development of the mineral industry while oil is still relevant as a source of wealth. The world is advancing daily with regards to innovation in science and technology championed by good education system. The movement is so fast that one wonders how Nigeria can surpass any of the new entrants into the G 20 nations. In order to achieve this, the relevant mining institutions in the country will need to be upgraded for capacity building in order to face the globe challenges, which, requires the mobility of human resources.

1. Enhancement of the Mining /Geo-Sciences Curriculum. The today's mining industry needs graduates who are not only technically sound in engineering, but who can progress quickly through supervision and into management. A mining engineer's chief responsibility is to exploit minerals out of the ground at the least cost and at the least devastation on the environmental. This is accomplished by mining engineers providing technical expertise in many areas, such as rock mechanics, ore reserve evaluation, mine design, equipment selection, and mine land reclamation. In the process, management-related concepts that the mining engineer deals with on a regular basis include health and safety, economics and finance, labour relations, project management, environmental management, and labour and environmental law. All of these concepts and more should desirably be included in the present Mining/Mineral Processing Engineering and Management degree curriculum. In addition to the above core subjects, the students in the various programmes will be required to take elective courses in Engineering and Construction Materials, Advanced Rock Mechanics, Computer Application in geosciences modeling, Rock slope engineering, Coal Mining, Engineering Project Management and Advanced Management Techniques.

2. Industrial Training. The operational problems of SIWES have obvious implications for the acquisition of technical skills and knowledge advancement. The disproportionately large number of students participating in the scheme makes adequate funding difficult by government, effective coordination by ITF and supervisory agencies. The students may see industrial attachment as a mere pre-condition of partial fulfillment of requirements for the award of certificates only, rather than as a vehicle for acquiring specific skills for meaningful contribution to the growth of industry and commerce. Greater commitment is required from the supervisory bodies and Institutions to ensure proper placements and supervision of students. The Programme should be centrally organized, monitored and certified by NBTE, Industrial Training Fund.

The mandatory wasteful 12 months industrial attachment programme for National Diploma graduates which presently provides eligibility for admission into Higher National Diploma (HND) be scrapped immediately. This mandatory exercise has proved to be fraudulent most times in view of the limited numbers of functional mining/mineral industries in the country. National Diploma graduates should pursue Higher National Diploma or Bachelor of Technology (B. Tech) programme in four years to avoid double painful admission exercise.

3. The Relevance of Information Technology. The importance of the information technology to the mineral industry has become a matter of necessity and far from a luxury. There is therefore an urgent need for government, the private sector and the general public to evolve a grand plan for the purpose of accelerating computer literacy and usage in our public business life. It is no longer acceptable for graduates of the Polytechnics in particular, to lack of an adequate working knowledge and usage of information technology. As a matter of national concern, computer education should best be introduced starting from the curriculum of Senior Secondary School. Computer Science should be made compulsory for all pupils in the SSCE, Federal and State Government should also evolve an aggressive on-the-job computer training programme for all their

work force as much as possible. Libraries should be fully computerized (with full internet connection) to ensure that our scholars can benefit from the amount of information now available to their counter parts in the industrialized nation

4. Teaching/Research Laboratory and Facilities. In order to ensure quality capacity building in the mineral industry ,as part of the undergraduate teaching and research programme all academic departments would require an extensive/ well-equipped laboratories and facilities or fieldwork such as the following: Digital total surveying equipment; Analogue and Digital Logging Units; Digitizing, Computing and Plotting Facilities; Rock Mechanics Testing Equipment; Mine Ventilation Simulation and Image analysis Systems; XRF and electron-excited Spectrometers; Atomic Absorption, UV and IR Spectrophotometers; X-ray Diffractometer; Scanning Electron Microscopes; Airborne Dust Sampling and Monitoring Units; Gas Chromatograph Analysis Equipment; High Temperature Furnaces; Pilot-scale Comminution and Mineral Separation Equipment; and Specialist Hydro and Pyrometallurgical Process Systems amongst others.

5. Institutional Specialization. Mining Institutions need to develop a niches in some specific areas, where they posses comparative advantages. The Institutions may for example specialize in any of the following: - Development of a new, safer, and more economical way to mine, transport and use coal, consider environmental problems created through the use and production of coal. Develop new uses and markets for coal energy fuels, and allied minerals. Development greater efficiency and conservation in mining and mineral industries and make such tests and investigations as may be required from the Federal Ministry of Steel Development the Mines Offices etc in the prosecution of its work. Conduct such experiments, tests and activities as will promote the development of the mineral industries in the state.

6. Partnership Strategy for Productive Education. The qualities of graduates produce presently are poorly skilled and knowledgeable. Through strategic partnership Nigeria can learn from the experiences of developed economies and the Asian Tigers by developing a strategy of international partnerships that targets specific training in productive skills and competent management, aimed at specific exports. The objective is to develop modern Institutions of mining that can train productive human resources by focusing on and establishing specific exports. This strategy has worked for Malaysia. There can be experiences to be shared and processes to be learned for modernizing education for practical development which Nigeria can adopt and adapt. From the experiences of the Asian Tigers successful capacity building initiatives can be achieved based on the following principles:

1. Project Based oversea Scholarships.
2. Training the Trainers, Managers and Technicians.
3. Export Focused Oversea Training.
4. Modernization of Institutions for Local training.
5. Expatriate Management Support for Local Training.

CONCLUSION

The essence of improved capacity building is to attempt to make a leap from the present stage and to emulate/ and or surpass more advanced developing countries like South Africa, Brazil, Malaysia and India who in spite of being amongst the present G20 are facing new problems that come with learning how to adopt and adapt cutting-edge technologies, and how to participate in global S & T systems. The aspiration is legitimate and realizable subject high political will to be placed on professional development of personnel through training and exposure to best international practices in the mineral industries.

The current best practice in capacity building is to integrate the knowledge of Mining Engineers/Mineral Processors and Geo-Scientist with competency in responsible mining practices to fast-track national economic growth and development. This will enable the mining engineer to take responsibility for the many dimensions of operations in a sustainable manner by integrating a diverse array of skills with professional competency. Emphasis must be placed on professional development of personnel through training and exposure to best international practices in the mineral industries. The aim is to facilitate innovative exploration, mining and mineral processing methods capable of addressing technical challenges and important social and environmental issues faced by the mineral sector.

REFERENCES

Abdullahi S.A. (2009). A New Vision 2020 for Nigeria at 49: Challenges and Possibilities. <file:///F:\Vision 2020 Nigeria Possibilities.htm>.

Abdulkarim S. (2009). Education and the Challenges of Globalization. Daily Trust Monday October, 26.th

Aina, Olu (1998). Professional Development of Polytechnic Graduates, Commonwealth Association of Polytechnics in Africa for International Conference. Kaduna

Costa S; Scoble M. (2009). An Interdisciplinary Approach to Integrating Sustainability into Mining engineering Education and Research. The Journal of Clean Production, Elsevier Science. file:\interdisciplinaryApproach.txt.

Mallo J.S. (1999) total Quality Management in Mineral Resources Development in Nigeria (MBA) Project submitted to School of Post Graduate Studies, ABU,, Zaria

Mallo S.J.(2000) Enhancing Manpower Development for the Mineral Industry in Nigeria. 8th NSME Conference, Jos.

Mallo S.J.(2003) Problems of Manpower Development for the Mineral Industry in Nigeria Nigerian Mining Journal Vol.4, Number 1 (pp.60-64), ISSN 1117-4307.

Mohammed Mahathir (2000). The Way Forward-Vision 2020. A paper presented by His Excellency to the Malaysian Business Council.

Olawuni, O.R. (1985). SIWES – A Bridge between Theory and Practice. A Paper Presented at the 5th Biennial SIWES National Conference

Olu Odeyemi (2000) Problems and Constraints of Post-ND Industrial Training, National Seminar on Improved Practical Training and Skills in Polytechnics Area House, Kaduna.

Paul Ryan (1991). International Comparisons of Vocational Education and Training for Intermediate skills. The Palma Press.

Yakubu N.A. (2008). The Role of Public Mining Institutions: Best Practices and Proposal for Reforms. A paper presented at the workshop on strategies for sustainable development of the solid minerals industry in Nigeria, NICON Hilton Hotel, Abuja, and 14-16 August.

International Monetary Fund, 2007

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